

An Open Preservation Framework for Digital Archaeological Data

Panagiotis Papageorgiou, Brett Stevens, Claire Bailey-Ross & Tarek Teba

ABSTRACT

The pace of adoption of new technologies from archaeologists could outstrip the development of infrastructure and policy to enable the preservation of the large volumes of new digital archaeological outputs. Therefore, there is a need for the archaeological community to prioritise a transition to proactive digital preservation (i.e. preservation-ready digital objects). This could facilitate an almost exclusive use of open formats for future preservation, and pave the way for the establishment of open licensing for obsolete versions of existing software.

This paper addresses the major preservation challenge of specifying an open documentation and metadata framework applicable to digital archaeological data. It suggests that a way towards the development of such a broad framework for the preservation of an archaeological research project's digital record can be initially, through, a meta-synthesis of relevant file format recommendations in the digital preservation literature, and subsequently, through the specification of their equivalent open formats. In doing so, the paper also touches on the issue of open licensing for preservation purposes.

Keywords: preservation framework, open formats, open licensing, meta-synthesis, digital documentary archive, proactive digital preservation

INTRODUCTION

In use in archaeology there is a wide range of surveying techniques including 3D modelling, laser scanning, rectified photography, panoramic imaging, and photogrammetry. They can offer great accuracy fast, but they also produce large data files, which require expensive and sophisticated hardware and software in order to view and post-process them. This ever-increasing number of legacy, and contemporary digital archaeological outputs are losing their original functionality and information richness because of poor digital preservation provision (Rieger et al. 2022). Consequently, archaeologists need to deposit this type of data in ‘trusted’ digital repositories where files are securely preserved, curated, and made permanently accessible.

As the provision of digital preservation remains limited across memory institutions, it has reached a point that needs to be determined by the value of the digital research outputs submitted to their collections. However, this can be difficult since the value of digital assets may not be evident for a long time. For example, archaeological virtual reconstructions which had little perceived significance at the time of their creation, often come to have much greater importance for future generations.

It thus becomes clear that the value of a digital archaeological record is in the surrounding context, not just the individual digital objects themselves. In particular, a complex digital archaeological object, such as an archaeological virtual reconstruction, and its accompanying documentation (metadata/paradata) are individually ‘worthless’ but rich in combination. This confirms that it is necessary to have a preservation strategy (where data is contextual and available for interpretation), rather than a storage strategy (where data is recorded without a context).

EFFECTIVE DIGITAL PRESERVATION

As a general rule, the appropriate preservation strategy is selected according to the unique combination of the nature of the digital objects which belong to the collection of a memory institution, and the needs of the designated communities (target audience). For instance, librarians are usually oriented towards collecting various types of metadata around deposited digital objects, but mostly for facilitating data retrieval. Nonetheless, effective digital preservation, at a minimum, has two parts: 1) Renderability (the ability to ‘execute’ and use a stored digital object), and 2) Understandability (the ability to interpret and understand the given object) (Giaretta, 2011). Hence, even at the minimum level, it is not sufficient to preserve only media and bits, as additional data is required for Understandability.

Having access to digital archaeological outputs, including archaeological virtual reconstructions, without their accompanying metadata is not enough. Different types of metadata are required to understand what they represent (Lavoie & Gartner, 2013) and how they were created, respectively. In the case of virtual reconstructions, information about the creative design process (virtual reconstruction

paradata) is required to support the scientific authenticity as well as the repeatability of, often, particularly expensive, and difficult to reproduce proprietary processes (Mitcham, 2012), i.e. only repeatable within a specific software package, with access to the archaeological decisions made at that specific time.

Digital archivists and relevant academics alike (Niven et al. 2013), have recurrently highlighted the significance of preserving the long-term accessibility to our virtual heritage for future reuse and reinterpretation. Both preservation staff and specialists assert that ‘scientifically authenticated’, i.e. transparent and validated methodological approach, archaeological virtual reconstructions provide field practitioners and members of the public the ability to ‘visit’ a structure remotely, to examine its otherwise inaccessible details, or to observe how it has changed over time (Forte, 2015). These are complex digital archaeological objects that contain more than just a creative artefact and also have scientific metadata and virtual reconstruction paradata attached to them. Therefore, there is a need to register the paradata (data about the creative design process), as well as the contextual information around entries of a digital documentary archive. When it comes to virtual reconstructions of monuments, contextual information can include the associated social and environmental context, e.g. flora and fauna (Lopez-Menchero & Grande, 2011), furniture or inhabitants. This is another indication that the focus is not on the importance of the individual digital files comprising the digital archaeological documentary archive but the history that the sum of them represents.

Returning to the concept of Renderability, it becomes clear that an effective preservation strategy for archaeological virtual reconstructions should be based on keeping the original look-and-feel of the digital objects, to preserve the cultural significance of the technological context in which they were created, as well as the archaeological information that they contain. Nevertheless, many archival employees do not have the necessary technical expertise to collect, understand, and make use of the required information for providing access to complex digital objects, such as archaeological virtual reconstructions. This indicates a need to define an open preservation framework applicable beyond the confines of virtual reconstructions of archaeological finds.

OPEN PRESERVATION FRAMEWORK FOR A DIGITAL DOCUMENTARY ARCHIVE

Published and open formats pose as the ideal candidate from a preservation perspective. The best options for long-term preservation are non-proprietary, open format specifications produced by international standards bodies (Todd, 2009). Usually numerous organisations have been involved in the development of these standards and they are generally backwards compatible (PARADIGM, 2008). Each of these formats is typically supported by equipment manufacturers for between ten and twenty years.

Several sources have previously specified optimal preservation formats for a digital archaeological documentary archive, although in most cases the recommended file formats are proprietary. Furthermore, various researchers have introduced the concept of preservation-ready digital objects for other domains (Gladney, 2008; Smith & Nelson, 2008), without emphasising the need for storing and depositing those using open formats and licenses. After comparing and contrasting existing standards and recommendations for preservation of different data types, this paper introduces an open file type framework for an archaeological research project that could ultimately include complex digital objects, such as virtual reconstructions.

To achieve this, a meta-synthesis of relevant recommendations (Trognitz et al. 2016) was conducted. Hence, it is suggested here that some recommendations can be made for open preservation file formats for the key data types typically included in an archaeological research project’s digital record, based on their interoperability across multiple platforms. Since the cost of proprietary software and licenses can be expensive, a shift from proprietary file formats to open types should be established.

In order to do this, archaeologists must, preferably, preserve all of the data used to form an archaeological project’s documentary archive in digital form, i.e. original data, intermediate data, and final artefacts. Additionally, ‘agreed in advance’ standards and processes as well as preservation of supporting documentation are necessary. For instance, the client’s specification (commission of archaeological work) and recording of the archaeological methodology, amongst other things, are prerequisites for preservation-ready objects. Sourcing this level of technical information during an archaeological research project could save digital preservationists time and effort, and hence cost, after the project has concluded. Archaeologists and other data originators thus become part of the preservation as they supply digital objects ready for preservation.

Moreover, by using open formats, the digital preservationists are assured that the data submitted will be preserved in the format in which was created by the originator, in a format they deemed to include the relevant content and context, rather than later be converted to an open format. The latter can result in losing important features of the original data. By specifying the equivalent open formats for the broader digital record of an archaeological project (Table 1), the data types which comprise an archaeological research project’s digital documentary archive are documented, as well as the context in which it was developed.

Table 1: A framework for the preservation of an archaeological research project’s digital record

<u>Data types of a documentary archive (digital form)</u>	<u>Open preservation file formats</u>
Spreadsheets (.xls)	.csv/.ods

Databases (.mdb/.dbf/.mdf)	.siard/.dbml/.json
Text (.doc)	.pdf/.xml/.odt/.txt
3D vector graphics (.wrl/.tnt/.gif)	.x3d/.dae/.u3d
Texture map and Reference images (.bmp/.jpg/.tga)	.png/.tif
3D point clouds (.ptx/.lgs)	.e57/.las
3D models (.max/.dwg/.cgr)	.x3d/.obj/.u3d
Rendered images (.jpg)	.png/.tif
Video (.mov/.avi)	.mxf/.mkv/.mp4
Creative design process (.psd/.xls/.doc)	.tif/.csv/.ods/.pdf/.xml/.txt

This then partially forms the virtual reconstruction paradata. As discussed above, virtual reconstruction paradata, as a form of metadata which records the creative design process, is particularly important for supporting the scientific transparency of an archaeological virtual reconstruction. For a virtual reconstruction to be valid, both its archaeological paradata and virtual reconstruction paradata needs to be associated. Every subsequent creative decision, as well as preservation activity associated with a virtual reconstruction need to be recorded as they change the original data into interpretation.

OPEN LICENSING FOR DIGITAL PRESERVATION PURPOSES

Along with the promotion of an almost exclusive use of open formats for future preservation, open licensing for preservation purposes also needs to be established for obsolete versions of already existing software. To be considered truly open, the recommended preservation framework should operate under an equally accessible legal framework that explicitly defines the fair use of the licenses of already obsolete software to be used later in the context of the existing preserved software. Thus, work needs to be done to define contracts with software suppliers, or work with digital preservationists to campaign for specific kinds of open licensing under certain terms and conditions both at a national and international level.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a large volume of digital archaeological outputs dating from around the beginning of the 21st century that are already becoming obsolete because of the recurrent technological changes, e.g. discontinuation of specific software versions, especially operating systems (Lindlar et al. 2014). These complex digital objects are usually deliverables of research projects investigating archaeological remains through virtual reconstruction, notwithstanding their associated context. There is a pressing

need for digital preservation frameworks that can include those as well as other digital archaeological outputs that are currently being produced.

This paper showed that just having access to a stored digital object, e.g. archaeological virtual reconstruction, without its accompanying metadata/paradata is not enough for preservation. Effective digital preservation occurs only when the provision of access to an obsolete (unreadable and no longer supported formats) digital object is complemented by the required metadata/paradata to understand what it represents and how it was created, respectively. In the case of virtual reconstructions, information about the creative design process is also required to support the scientific authenticity as well as the repeatability of, often, particularly expensive, and difficult to reproduce proprietary processes, i.e. only repeatable within a specific software package, with access to the archaeological decisions made at that specific time.

This paper suggests the use of open formats during the research processes of an archaeological project rather than the use of proprietary formats. By using open formats, the digital preservationists are assured that the deposited data will be preserved in the format as close to how it was originally created (preservation-ready objects). The recommended open formats for the broader digital record of an archaeological project (Table 1) is important as it documents the cultural context in which an archaeological excavation project was undertaken, and partially forms the paradata for the creative design process.

REFERENCES

- [1] Boutard, J., Guastavino, C. & Turner, J. (2013). A Digital Archives Framework for the Preservation of Artistic Works with Technological Components. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 8(1), 42–65. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v8i1.237>
- [2] Forte, M. (2015). Cyber Archaeology: A Post-virtual Perspective. In P. Svensson, & D.T. Goldberg (Eds.), *Between Humanities and the Digital* (pp. 295-309). MIT Press.
- [3] Giaretta, D. (2011). *Advanced Digital preservation*. Springer.
- [4] Gladney, H.M. (2008). Durable Digital Objects Rather Than Digital preservation and Professional Implications. *Electronic Resource Preservation and Access Network ePRINTS Service*.
- [5] Lavoie, B. & Gartner, R. (2013). *Preservation Metadata* (2nd ed.) (Report 13-03). Digital preservation Coalition. <https://doi.org/10.7207/twr13-03>

- [6] Lindlar, M., Saemann, H., Ochmann, S., Gadiraju, U., & Jonsson, O. (2014). *Current state of 3D object digital preservation and gap-analysis report* (Report D6.6.1). Durable Architectural Knowledge. European Commission.
- [7] Lopez-Mencheró, V.M. & Grande, A. (2011). The Principles of the Seville Charter. In International Committee of Architectural Photography, International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, & International Council on Monuments and Sites (Eds.), *23rd CIPA symposium*. CIPA Heritage Documentation.
- [8] Mitcham, J. (2012). Preservation of Digital Objects at the Archaeology Data Service. In J. Delve, D. Anderson, M. Dobrevá, D. Baker, C. Billenness, & L. Konstantelos (Eds.), *Preservation of Complex Objects: Volume 1: Visualisations and Simulations* (pp. 76–85). University of Portsmouth.
- [9] Niven, K., Jeffrey, S., & Richards, J.D. (2013). Archiving Three-Dimensional Archaeology: New Technologies, New Solutions? In G. Earl, T. Sly, A. Chrysanthi, P. Murietta-Flores, C. Papadopoulos, I. Romanowska, & D. Wheatley (Eds.), *Archaeology in the Digital Era: Volume II* (pp. 289–294). Amsterdam University Press.
- [10] Personal Archives Accessible in Digital Media (2008). *Preservation metadata*. <https://wayback.archive-it.org/org-467/20161101120848/http://www.paradigm.ac.uk/workbook/metadata/preservation-types.html>
- [11] Rieger, O.Y., Schonfeld, R.C. & Sweeney, L. (2022). *The Effectiveness and Durability of Digital Preservation and Curation Systems*. ITHAKA. <https://doi.org/10.18665/sr.316990>
- [12] Smith, J.A. & Nelson, M.L. (2008). Creating Preservation-Ready Web Resources. *D-Lib Magazine*, 14(1/2). <https://doi.org/10.1045/january2008-smith>
- [13] Todd, M. (2009). *File formats for preservation* (Report 09-02). Digital preservation Coalition. <https://doi.org/10.7207/twr09-02>
- [14] Trognitz, M., Niven, K. & Gilissen, V. (2016). *3D Models in Archaeology: A Guide to Good Practice*. Archaeology Data Service. https://guides.archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/g2gp/3d_Toc